

SRM'S IN CHEMICAL MONITORING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The need for standards for physical measurements has been recognized as far back as the days of the Egyptian pharaohs and the use of the cubit as a unit of length. Since that time, increased measurement sophistication has led to the need for accurate physical standards of measurement. The development of the metric system and subsequently the International System of Units (SI), has in many ways met the need for primary standards for physical measurements.

The accurate measurement of chemical properties is a more recent need. While the chemical measurement system and the network that goes with it borrows heavily from the physical measurement system, it is in many ways more fragmented. This paper explores the use of chemical measurement systems and their role in obtaining and verifying highly accurate and precise measurements over a long period of time. Also included in the discussion is a review of currently available Standard Reference Materials appropriate to ocean science and monitoring.

The concept of a system of standards for physical measurements has been recognized since ancient times. It was employed in Egypt by the Pharaohs, recognized by our founding fathers in the Constitution and, in its latest form, has been addressed internationally for more than 100 years. As currently conceived the system is referred to as the International System of Units or the SI System. This system incorporates natural definitions for many of the primary units (length, time, temperature, etc.).

In the area of chemical measurements, the SI system also provides the analytical chemist with units describing the amount of substance (mole), mass (kilogram), and others. But because of problems in applying these defined primary units in the measurement of chemical composition, appropriate "matrix-matched" materials can be very helpful. These materials usually resemble as closely as possible the material being analyzed. They are measured by an independent laboratory or group of laboratories and issued by a certifying authority with a certificate describing the characteristics or content of the components of

interest. The need for and use of these matrix-matched materials as a reference base has long been recognized in some areas of analytical chemistry. In 1905 the American Foundrymen's Association approached NBS with their need for cast iron materials to standardize analytical measurements for the quality control of cast iron production. This effort was so successful and so important to the measurement of cast irons that subsequent issues of the same material are still being distributed today by NBS. Further, the use of these Certified Reference Materials (or as NBS refers to them, Standard Reference Materials or SRM's) is recognized industry-wide as "accepted quality assurance practice" and even though the industry sells its product based largely on compositional specifications, there are relatively few measurement disagreements.

While the American Foundrymen's Association recognized the need for SRM's early on, a number of other scientific areas have also utilized Reference Materials to improve measurement systems and to make analytical measurement more reliable. An example of this is the National Institute of Neurological and Communicative Disorders and Stroke which came to NBS with a request to develop SRM's for the measurement of antiepilepsy drugs in serum. The result of this effort was the issuance of three serum materials with graded concentration ranges for the four drugs. Following the issuance of these materials a review of measurements from five reference laboratories showed an improvement of precision by a factor of 2 to 3 due solely to the introduction of the SRM's.

An area of measurement more appropriate to the interests of this conference is the study of the atmospheric carbon dioxide and the global carbon cycle by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Energy Research. Understanding the cycle and the growth of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere requires that highly precise and repeatable measurements be made by a number of monitoring stations over long intervals of time because the essential factor is the change in carbon dioxide content over time and by location. Thus all measurements in this measurement system, regardless of the laboratories' location or measuring equipment must be compatible with each other. To a large extent the pioneering

standardization by C. D. Keeling of the Scripps Institution of Oceanography has contributed to the reliability of these measurements and form a basis for much of the modeling and understanding of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere today. Building on that beginning, NBS is now providing SRM's which can help assure accuracy in this measurement system.

Using the examples just presented as a justification for incorporating Standard Reference Materials into a measurement system, it is appropriate to review the availability of SRM's for those interested in oceanography and marine science. The National Bureau of Standards through the Office of Standard Reference Materials has developed a number of these materials. Included are materials for the analysis of water, sediment, and biological tissue. Some of these materials are certified for trace elements and some are certified for organic pollutants. Others are certified for radioactivity.

For the analysis of trace elements in water, SRM 1643, a stabilized and acidified solution containing trace elements has been developed. It is currently available as SRM 1643b and is certified for 20 elements at levels that range from 8 to 200 ng/mL. It is primarily intended for evaluating the accuracy of trace determinations in filtered and acidified water. Two other SRM's have been developed specifically for the determination of mercury in water. SRM 1641b is designed for the preparation of calibration solutions and for use as a "spike" sample in the method of additions analytical procedure. The material is certified at 1.52 µg/mL. SRM 1642b is designed for use as received and contains 1.49 ng/mL of mercury. In addition to these materials, a simulated rainwater has been developed to aid in the analysis of acidic rainwater. It is composed of two water samples at different levels of acidity and is certified for specific conductance, acidity, also F^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_3^+ , Ca^{++} , and Mg^{++} concentration. In conjunction with these measurements, NBS also offers a series of buffer materials for the calibration of pH measurements. Likewise, sodium chloride, potassium chloride and potassium fluoride are available for the calibration of ion-selective electrodes.

For the measurement of organic compounds in water several appropriate SRM's are available. These include seven priority halocarbons present at ng/µL levels in a halocarbon solution designated as SRM 1639. The halocarbons are chloroform, chlorodibromomethane, bromodichloromethane, bromoform, carbon tetrachloride, trichloroethylene, and tetrachloroethylene. SRM 1647, Priority Pollutant Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons (in Acetonitrile) is also available. It consists of certified concentrations of 16 polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH's) that the EPA has identified as priority pollutants.

Certified Concentrations of
Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons in SRM 1647

<u>Compound</u>	<u>Concentration, µg/mL</u>
Naphthalene	22.5
Acenaphthalene	19.1
Acenaphthene	21.0
Fluorene	4.92
Phenanthrene	5.06
Anthracene	3.29
Fluoranthene	10.1
Pyrene	9.84
Benz[a]anthracene	5.03
Chrysene	4.68
Benzo[b]fluoranthene	5.11
Benzo[k]fluoranthene	5.02
Benzo[a]pyrene	5.30
Benzo[ghi]perylene	4.01
Dibenz[a,h]anthracene	3.68
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene	4.06

Also, for the measurement of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons, a generator column designated as SRM 1644 has been developed to produce known, accurate concentrations of anthracene, benzo(a)anthracene (1,2-benzanthracene), and benzo(a)pyrene (3,4-benzopyrene) in water. These low-solubility compounds range from 1-50 µg/kg (ppb) based on column conditions as specified in the certificate.

Sediment and core materials have long been of interest to oceanographers. For the measurement of these materials, an estuarine sediment was developed with the support of the Virginia Institute of Marine Sciences at Gloucester Point, Virginia, who supplied the material. The NBS Estuarine Sediment, SRM 1646, is certified for the concentrations of 16 elements and uncertified (information) values for the concentrations of 19 other elements are provided.

SRM 1646, Estuarine Sediment

Certified Constituents

<u>Element</u>	<u>Concentration, wt. %</u>
Al	6.25
Ca	0.83
Fe	3.35
Mg	1.09
P	.054
	<u>Concentration, µg/g</u>
As	11.6
Cd	0.36
Cr	76
Co	10.5
Cu	18
Mn	375
Hg	.063
Ni	32
Pb	28.2
V	94
Zn	138

In addition to the estuarine sediment, a fresh water River Sediment, SRM 1645, is also available. This material was obtained from a highly industrialized area located on the Great Lakes and contains high levels of iron and chromium as well as many other elements associated with industrial pollution. It is certified for 18 elements with 8 other elements and 5 other chemical properties provided for information purposes only. Current plans call for the certification of a replacement for this material within the next year. The designated material, while from an industrial environment, is not expected to have such high concentrations of many of the industrial pollutants and thus should be of more general use.

Over a long period of time NBS has developed a number of minerals and ores certified for major and minor constituents. While these materials have limited interest to oceanographers, they should be mentioned because they serve to verify measurement techniques applicable to marine sediment. These materials include Flint Clay, Plastic Clay, Dolomitic Limestone, Argillaceous Limestone, Obsidian Rock, Basalt Rock, and Glass Sand.

For the analysis of organics that may be present in sediments there are several SRM's that are of interest and described here.

SRM 1583, Chlorinated Pesticides in 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane, contains certified concentrations for five chlorinated pesticides in 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (isooctane). These are γ -BHC (lindane), σ -BHC, aldrin, 4,4'-DDE, and 4,4'-DDT. An uncertified concentration is provided for heptachlor epoxide. Concentrations range from approximately 0.8 to 1.9 µg/g.

SRM 1586, Isotopically Labeled and Unlabeled Priority Pollutants in Methanol, is composed of two solutions: one containing ten priority pollutants at µg/g levels in methanol; the other containing the same priority pollutants, isotopically labeled with deuterium or carbon-13, at approximately the same concentrations in methanol. The compounds are: carbon tetrachloride, benzene, chlorobenzene, phenol, nitrobenzene, 2-nitrophenol, 2,4-dichlorophenol, naphthalene, bis[2-ethylhexyl]phthalate, and benzo(a)pyrene.

SRM 1614, Dioxin (2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin) in Isooctane, consists of separate solutions of unlabeled and labeled 2,3,7,8-TCDD. It is intended primarily for use in the accurate determination of 2,3,7,8-TCDD and can also be used for spiking samples for recovery studies, or to fortify samples with known amounts of 2,3,7,8-TCDD.

In this category, there are two oils that may also be of interest to the analyst. One, Petroleum Crude Oil, SRM 1582, is useful not only in the analysis of petroleum crude oil, but also in evaluating the accuracy of trace organic analytical methods for other oils, such as coal-derived liquid fuels. Certified concentrations are provided for fluoranthene, benzo[a]pyrene, perylene, benz[a]anthracene, dibenzothiophene, and phenanthrene. The other, Polychlorinated Biphenyls in Oil, SRM 1581, consists of certified concentrations of Aroclor 1242 and Aroclor 1260 present individually at 100 µg/g in motor oil and transformer oil. Additional base oil is supplied to dilute the four certified concentrations and expand the usefulness of this material.

Of interest to many marine chemists and oceanographers is the analysis of marine tissue. For many years the NBS has distributed a freeze-dried albacore tuna designated as RM 50. While this material is not certified, the report of investigation provides valuable informational data on the levels of Hg, Se, Zn, As, Pb, and several other elements. The major drawback of this material is the inclusion of bone tissue that is not homogeneously distributed, thus the measurement of some bone seeking elements is not reliable.

Of considerable interest is the freeze-dried Oyster Tissue that has been offered as SRM 1566. This material is currently out-of-stock. A new material has been obtained but to date, homogeneity has not been satisfactory for an SRM quality material and further processing is needed.

SRM 1577a, Freeze-Dried Bovine Liver, while not a marine tissue, is a biological tissue that may be of interest to marine chemists. It is certified for 5 minor and 18 trace constituents. Non-certified information is provided for 5 additional elements.

Since most instrumental methodologies commonly used for the analysis of marine materials do not give absolute concentrations of analytes, it is important to evaluate instrument performance in order to reduce both random and systematic errors. Instrument makers have made great improvements in instrumentation with the development of stable and highly linear electronic detection equipment and computerization of data acquisition and data processing equipment. These all enhance the ability to collect and process data but at the same time they tend to mask certain errors by obscuring the algorithms used for processing the data and overstating the reliability or the precision of the data. For that reason, it is frequently helpful to use instrument performance Standard Reference Materials to verify performance or to document the status of instruments used to acquire data. Such SRM's as the neutral absorbance glass filter, the GC-MS solution materials, and the holmium oxide solution wavelength material all serve to measure/eliminate such sources of bias. Similarly, the spectrometric solutions SRM's (2121-2129) that contain single elements (most at 10 ng/mL concentration) are useful in preparing working standards for ICP, AA, and other techniques requiring solution standards. In addition, they are extremely valuable in evaluating the effects of interference in the instrument measurement process.

Standard Reference Materials from the U.S. NBS have been discussed in this paper but Reference Materials are internationally important and available from a wide range of sources throughout the world. An excellent document describing the availability of these materials is the NOAA report, Standard and Reference Materials, by Adriana Y. Cantillo (in press).

Whatever the source, Certified Reference Materials lend credibility to measurements and all extensive analytical monitoring/measuring networks should employ them to validate their measurement program. Everyone realizes the cost of making analytical measurements--the scientist's salary, the cost of equipment and many times the cost of acquiring the sample itself. If all of these are considered, the economic cost of making measurements is extremely high, but the cost of making bad measurements is equally high but without value. Thus the cost of tying measurements to the national measurement system and verifying the quality of the measurements through the use of Standard Reference Materials is small relative to the value added. In addition to the economic argument, poor measurements and measurements without authentication should be eliminated in order to make our understanding of natural ocean phenomena more accurate and less confusing.

Support for the development of CRM's by governmental agencies is limited and demands for CRM's are expanding. Those who plan and undertake the establishment of monitoring networks for our oceans and estuaries must speak soon and often to be sure the resources are available to develop needed CRM's.